

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING FOR FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES PRODUCED BY THE WINDING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the power density as a ratio of internal pressure to mass of pressure vessels has steadily increased, which is particularly advantageous for the transportation of gases as fuel in vehicles. At the same time, high safety requirements combined with a high degree of lightweight construction usually correlate with an increased demand for cost-intensive high-performance materials. Also with the increasing introduction of hydrogen-powered vehicles, high safety measures play a central role for pressure vessels, which are usually serially manufactured. In order to provide progressive series solutions for this, new safety systems are moving into the focus of scientific efforts.

Within the scope of intensive research work, the complete integration of a metallic sensor wire for the deformation measurement of a fibre-plastic composite pressure vessel as well as its functional verification is therefore being investigated. The structural integration of the sensor wire is based on a direct method, the so-called winding process. In the winding process, the reinforcing fibres are applied to a positive core. This results in closed moulded bodies in fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) design such as pipes, tanks, axles, pressure vessels and shafts. With the aid of a winding machine, a core (mandrel), which forms the shape of the component, is set in rotation and the reinforcing fibre is pulled off a creel with a defined yarn tension. At the same time, the sensor wire is fed through the same thread eye. The sensor wire thus follows the reinforcing fibre. This results in an exact positioning of the sensor wire along the reinforcing fibers and allows the measurement according to the stress of the composite structure.

For the impregnation of the reinforcement fibres with the resin system, these are passed through a resin bath and then wound onto the mandrel. Furthermore, the impregnation of the sensor wires is carried out indirectly via contact of the sensor wires with the impregnated reinforcement fibres. Rotation speed and thread eye position influence the thread and sensor orientation on the mandrel. Thus, the winding process permits the integration of sensor wires and is particularly suitable for load-path adapted orientation of the reinforcing fibers. The starting material for fulfilling the mechanical properties are reinforcing fibers in their most cost-effective form. Circumferential layers give the pressure vessel tangential strength. This type of fibre orientation is decisive in the event of failure, which makes structural health monitoring (SHM) of the circumferential layers in operation a sensible option. Its structure, the metrological basic principle and the behaviour under different load conditions are the subject of this article.

1 INTRODUCTION

Demands for CO₂-reduced drives and sustainable use of resources are forcing a surge of innovation in the "mobility of tomorrow", whereby battery-operated vehicles are increasingly establishing themselves in urban traffic structures. In order to be able to replace conventional drive concepts in long-distance operations, automobile manufacturers and political institutions are increasingly relying on hydrogen-powered vehicles based on fuel cells (FC). The Hyundai ix35 fuel cell and Toyota Mirai vehicles have been proving that this technology is ready for series production since 2013 and 2014. In addition, so-called fast followers, such as Daimler AG, are announcing further vehicles with fuel cells for the coming years. Slow followers such as Audi and BMW are also forecasting their market launch for zero-emission FC vehicles in 2020 and 2025. Fig. 1 illustrates a number of FC vehicles in order of their already completed and forecast series launch.

Figure 1: Already completed and forecast series starts of FC vehicles in Germany

High safety requirements for the storage modules required for this, such as pressure vessels made of FRP, usually correlate with an increased demand for cost-intensive high-performance materials (carbon fibres) or equally cost-intensive procedures for monitoring the condition of the FRP structure. However, in order to pave the way for series solutions, new, cost-efficient safety concepts must be brought into the focus of technical and scientific efforts. The focus here is on increasing the component safety of wound FRP components without further over-dimensioning the structure. The state of the art does not yet provide sufficient solutions for this. For this reason, a very inexpensive direct process with the basic principle of classical strain gauges is proposed and examined in more detail. The scientific investigations focus on the direct integration of the sensors during the component manufacturing process without increased additional effort in production, a robust and proven measuring technique and very inexpensive sensor materials.

2 KNOWN METHODS FOR INTEGRATED STRAIN MEASUREMENT OF FIBER-PLASTIC COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

In addition to local measuring methods such as strain gauges with measuring grid arrangements made of copper-nickel alloys, micro strain gauges, foil strain gauges, aerosol-printed strain gauges or optical fibres with fibre Bragg gratings developed especially for fibre composites, a solution suitable for fibres is also available for structure monitoring. The sensors can be inserted into different layers of the fiber composite component during production or subsequently applied. For the measurement of component deformations, the different methods have established themselves, which, however, fail for large series applications due to economic implementation [1].

2.1 Classic strain gauges

Despite existing variants of adapted strain measurement systems for fibre composite structures, their handling due to cable faults and the measurement results due to inaccurate positioning and unevenness of the structure itself have so far not been satisfactory. Beyond that, conventional strain gauges are difficult to integrate into the production process. In addition, contacting is often associated with fiber damage, for example when contacting points are covered by resin. Furthermore, the influence of the temperature during the production of the composites plays a decisive role, since the strain measurement systems are usually subject to a temperature curve due to the production process. In addition, locally measurable strains in strain gage systems are disadvantageous for global structure monitoring. If the strain gage is applied exclusively to the surface, this effect is intensified, since not all individual layers of the laminate are included in the measurement and thin resin layers prevent direct contact with the fiber composite.

2.2 Fiber Bragg Grating

With fiber Bragg gratings (FBG), the length change is measured by measuring the Bragg wavelength of the embedded FBG in the optical fibers. The reflected wavelength at the Bragg grating changes proportionally to its elongation caused by mechanical or thermal loads. In detail, the reflected wavelength is equally dependent on both strain and temperature, making it necessary to separate the corresponding effects in order to obtain an accurate strain measurement [3]. The temperature compensation of fiber-optic sensors with FBG is carried out, for example, with the help of the fluorescence lifetime method. The light of a laser diode is fed to the sensor, which consists of an erbium and ytterbium doped glass fiber. The fluorescence effect results from the excitation of the ions, which leads to a change in the particle energy. This energy is emitted according to the decay law as spontaneous emission of light in a certain wavelength. The intensity of the light emission shows a temperature-dependent exponential decrease with time, whose connection with the temperature is usually non-linear. The method requires an additional doping of the optical fibers, an increased effort by generation or coupling of the exciting light, detectors for recording and an individual calibration due to the non-linear relationship between temperature and emitted wavelength [3, 4]. Successful applications of FBG in FKV demonstrate, for example, sensor rock anchors made of pultruded glass fibre reinforced plastic [3] and on-board pressure vessels for space application [5].

Classical optical fibres with FBG generally consist of a single-mode fibre core, a fibre sheath (gladding), the coating and a protective sheath. The fiber core has a very small diameter compared to the outer protective sheath.

The accuracy of the fibre optical sensors (FOS) with FBG in pressure vessels with carbon fiber epoxy resin systems is very low compared to applied strain gauge measurements and finite element calculations in the center of the cylinder and the circumferentially wound layers with a deviation of -1.2 %. In the outer circumferential layers the deviation is up to 11 %. Sensors in cross windings show a deviation of -1.6 % in the cylinder and 24 % at the pressure vessel ends [6]. The practical suitability for continuous remote monitoring of pressure vessels with integrated FOS with FBG is assessed as very good due to the deformation history and the linear relationship between Bragg wavelength and internal pressure. Optical sensors are also used to detect Armino concentrations in thermosetting resin systems [7, 8]. The example of a thin-walled multilayer composite of carbon fiber-reinforced polyamide (PA), produced by the winding process, illustrates its local effect. In comparison to the undisturbed cross-section with a composite wall thickness of about 800 μm , the integrated FOS with FBG without protective cover requires a magnification of $S_F = 1530 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 2). The protective sheath of the FOS was removed so that only the gladding ($\varnothing_G = 870 \mu\text{m}$) envelops the core with coating ($\varnothing_C = 190 \mu\text{m}$) as external protection.

Figure 2: Centrally arranged FOS with FBG in an FRP consisting of four layers of carbon fibre reinforced PA

In addition, the microscopic investigations show local changes of the FRP structure in the form of micro-notches, fiber reorientations and delamination, which can lead macroscopically to premature failure of the overall structure.

2.3 Piezoelectric sensor systems

In recent decades, piezoelectric sensors using the so-called direct piezo effect have proven to be an essential instrument for measuring various processes. Due to the comparatively high mechanical stiffness of piezo ceramic materials ($E \sim 70 \text{ GPa}$), the good electromechanical response at very small deformations ($\epsilon < 1 \%$) and the pronounced linearity over wide temperature ranges (applications up to $1,000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), piezo ceramic materials are suitable as sensor elements for various applications.

Piezoelectric sensors convert mechanical quantities directly into electrical quantities. They are used for the indirect determination of different physical quantities, such as force, pressure or acceleration, and are used in quality as well as process control and as a versatile development tool in various industries. For example, piezoelectric sensors are used in numerous application areas such as automotive engineering, aerospace, medical technology and nuclear technology [9, 10].

Piezoelectric sensor modules essentially consist of the mechanical transmission element, the housing and the piezo ceramic element, which is pre-assembled as a monolithic ceramic with electrical surface contacts or as a stack with an interdigital electrode structure and connecting wires. Such sensors can be found, for example, as pressure sensors in cylinders for knock detection in combustion engines and in injection moulding tools for process control of cavity pressure, for layer thickness measurement in thin-film coating processes (e.g. with PVD: physical vapour deposition) or as ultrasonic transducers for distance measurement in systems for parking assist systems.

Another field of application is the piezoelectric strain measurement, in which the displacement change acting on the sensor is converted into a force. The piezoelectric elements in the sensor, which are essentially subjected to shear stress, generate an electrical charge Q (pC) proportional to this force [11, 12]. Special advantages compared to classical strain measurement are the immunity to electromagnetic fields, the high sensitivity, the high overload safety and the practically unlimited durability, whereby piezoelectric strain sensors exhibit a drift due to their principle [13].

2.4 Carbon based composites used for strain measurement

Nanomaterials such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and industrial carbon black are promising materials for sensor applications. In macroscopic films, they form a conductive network at low concentrations. Thermoplastic nanocomposites filled with carbon nanotubes or industrial carbon black and their combinations exhibit electrical conductivities ranging from $\sigma < 10^{-8}$ S/m for insulators to $\sigma > 10^6$ S/m for electrical conductors, depending on the internal network structure. The physical properties, in particular the electrical conductivity of such heterogeneous polymer systems, are mainly determined by the structure of the internal network; see e.g. [14, 15, 16, 17]. This depends essentially on the configuration and morphology of the carbon filler, the polymer and its processing parameters. Therefore, these carbon based nanocomposites show excellent electro-mechanical behaviour and – due to a high sensitivity between the total resistance of a CNT/polymer resistor and an acting mechanical stress – can be used e.g. as strain gauge on hybrid components [18] or embedded in fibre reinforced composites [19].

2.5 Embroidered textile-metal hybrid sensors as special form of strain gauges

The processes described are based on the materials used, such as optical fibers and piezoelectric sensors, and are cost-intensive and time-consuming to process, making them unsuitable for medium to large series components. Alternatives are sensors based on metallic wires. The process for their manufacture allows electrical conductors to be sewn or embroidered onto a textile in a variety of forms and in a simple manner. This results in electrical structures with very good suitability for strain, temperature and level measurements. The extremely inexpensive materials and evaluation electronics assign a series character to the procedure. According to the design variants, the carrier material consists of a fleece, fabric or scrim with glass or polymer threads. At the beginning of the sensor manufacturing process, the sensor wire is located on a spool attached close to the sewing point with a defined unwinding torque.

During a classic sewing process with top and bottom thread, the sensor wire is fed and fixed to the embroidery ground. The measuring signal from the textile is fed to the measuring bridge with the aid of soldering support points and copper wires (see also [20] and [21]). The measuring principle is based on the bridge circuit developed by Sir Wheatstone in 1843 (so-called Wheatstone measuring bridge). Its originally assigned task is the determination of electrical resistances, both of absolute values and of relative resistance changes (basic principle of strain measurement). The measuring bridge consists of four ohmic resistances, furthermore two resistances each are assigned to one of two voltage dividers connected in parallel. The output voltage is distributed among the resistors according to their size ratio. If the voltage dividers are equally distributed, no current flows between the resistor pairs and the measuring bridge is considered to be calibrated (calibration condition fulfilled). In the case of a quarter bridge, one of the four resistors is variable (strain gauge). All other resistors are designed as fixed resistors. With the resistors and the change of the resistance due to strains, a change of the bridge voltage takes place depending on the magnitude of the output voltage.

Test series on a pressure vessel with steel liner and carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) as winding structure describe the acquisition and analysis of strains during a filling process with the aid of strain sensors specially designed for this application. For this purpose, textile-engineered stick sensors are applied [22]. Wires made of metal alloys are embroidered onto a polyester fleece and then laminated onto the steel liner and into the fibre composite structure. The orientation corresponds to the main stress directions of a closed pipe under internal pressure. Test series on a Type III pressure vessel show measured strains as a function of a pulsating pressure load up to 350 bar in tangential direction (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Pressure and strain curve (tangential) of a type III pressure vessel with CFRP reinforcement; incl. illustration of an embroidered and applied tangential sensor

Liner and FRP structure describe an almost identical elongation behavior, measured by the mean values. Consequently, a consideration of the strains of the entire component can be transferred to adjacent individual layers and the liner in the global coordinate system. The different amplitudes of the strains also support previous investigations of the damping behavior of FKV [23].

3 DIRECT INTEGRATION OF A METALLIC WIRE AS A STRAIN SENSOR

With the help of the structure-integrated sensor system, real-time monitoring of selected layers in the FKV pressure vessel (CPV) is aimed at. The sensor system consists of one or more metallic wires and associated measuring technology, such as a measuring amplifier, a wheatstone bridge circuit and a PC with corresponding software. In order to guarantee the complete function of the wires in the component, their position in the component is of great importance. For this reason, the wires are applied in the same process step as the FRP structure of the CPV. Classical fiber winding has proven to be a suitable process. In this process, reinforcing fibers are drawn off from a braked bobbin creel with constant yarn tension, deflected several times and fed to a core rotating about the longitudinal axis via a yarn eye movable in several axes. At the same time, the threads are impregnated online with a resin system (thermoset plating), or the FRP structure is formed by welding thermoplastic tapes onto the core (tape winding). The latter requires an energy source and completely impregnated and consolidated tapes, which worsens the energy balance compared to thermoset winding, but increases the process speed significantly. Depending on the type of material processing, the wire feed for thermoset winding takes place before the thread eye and for tape winding after the thread eye with the aid of a separate wire-tape feed. For this purpose, there is an unwinding station on the winding machine which resembles a bobbin creel in its basic function. The configuration of the unwinding station depends essentially on the properties of the sensor wires, the properties of which must therefore be determined in each individual case.

3.1 Direct integration of the sensor wire into the FRP structure

The underlying principle is based on the use of cost-effective materials and their processing without any further process step. Metal wires are used for this purpose, their acquisition costs are below

1 €-cent/m and at the same time they are easy to process. In comparison to commercially available measuring elements based on metal wires, such as printed and embroidered strain gages, the sensor is created when the reinforcing structure is applied and is thus integrated into the component along the lines of force flow following the reinforcing fibre. The following Fig. 4 illustrates the process principle in three stages.

Figure 4: Process steps for integrating and constructing the sensor in the CPV: a) unwinding the wires, b) joining the wires with the reinforcing fibers, c) applying the wires on the mandrel along the reinforcing fibers

The special feature of the winding machine used here is a sensor wire unwinding station flanged onto the resin bath. This allows the sensor wires to be fed into the reinforcing fibres, which are applied to the mandrel along the prevailing load paths. The sensor wire unwinding point is integrated into the winding machine in such a way that there is no influence on the guidance of the reinforcing fibre, but the sensor wire unwinding point can follow the movement of the thread eye. This is necessary in order to reduce wire deflections to a minimum, which lead to damage of the wires or their coating. In addition, there is no functional influence on the winding machine, so that there are no restrictions apart from feeding the winding machine with reinforcing fibers and resin and in the movement of the axes.

3.2 Characteristic properties of the wires

The determination of the influencing factors is considered in the following with reference to the unwinding point. In detail, the determination of the maximum pull-off force is carried out by means of fundamental parameters determined in the tensile test, such as yield strength and elongation at break. Parallel data, such as the stiffness and tensile strength of the wires, can be of overriding interest for the characteristics of the individual layer with regard to the design of the overall component, so that this information is also given. The diagram in Fig. 5 shows the stress-strain curve of the wires Manganin© and ISA-Nickel© used in the project compared to steel S235 and two selected FKV materials.

Figure 5: Stress-strain diagram of ISA-Nickel© and Manganin© in comparison to steel and selected FRP

The diagram shows one curve each representing the entire set of curves of a material. In addition, the diagram contains information on the specimen structure and statistical data on the material properties. To clamp the wires in the tensile testing machine, cardboard specimen grips are used to clamp one wire each with a cross-section of 100 μm completely, straight and with low pretension in the testing machine. In the first step (Fig. 5: Step 1), the wire is fixed with adhesive to one half of the specimen carrier cut in advance and then the second half is joined concentrically (Fig. 5: Step 2). After clamping into the testing machine, the webs connecting the two halves can be cut (Fig. 5: Step 3) and tested with a preload of 0.3 N and 2 mm/min.

The evaluation of the tensile tests shows that the sensor alloys have a mechanical behavior typical for metals with a linear-elastic range, pronounced yield strength and elongations with a multiple of fiber-plastic composites. Due to the high elongations, the selected materials are basically suitable for use in FRP. However, their plastic behaviour under higher stresses leads to changes in the electrical conductivity and thus in the ohmic resistance, caused by restructuring of the metallic lattice in the form of dislocation shifts to the grain boundaries and reorientation of the alloying elements. For this reason, a displacement of the Hookschen straight line along the strain axis is absolutely necessary in order to ensure linearity of the measurements. This can be achieved, for example, by a one-time loading of the component above the test pressure (autofrettage). In addition to elongation at break, the force when the yield point is reached, is an important variable for process design. Exceeding the force values for ISA-Nickel© of about 4.0 N and for Manganin© tin of about 2.2 N generally leads to plastic deformation of the wires and thus to a change in cross-section, whereby the calculated length of the wires per layer with the aid of the conductor resistance deviates from the true length and thus has a negative influence on the measurement result.

3.3 Integration of the sensor wires in glass fibre reinforced plastic

The unwinding of the reinforcing fibres took place with a yarn tension of 10 N on the standardised

winding machine. The sensor wires made of Manganin[®] and ISA-Nickel[®] followed the fibre bundle through the thread eye. All wires used were in a dry roving. The impregnation was subsequently carried out with the aid of a brush.

A solder board was used for contacting the sensor wires. On this board all wires are soldered on one side. On the opposite side there are copper wires. This simplifies the contacting with the measurement setup considerably.

3.4 Verification of the measurement system

In a first test, the pressure vessel was subjected to an internal pressure of up to 260 bar (see Fig. 6, left). The blue curve shows the half-bridge circuit and the red curve the quarter-bridge circuit. In a first phase, only measurable values from about 30 bar could be written out. This is due to a very stiff behavior of the CPV in the lower pressure range, since further measurements show very high resolutions. In the further course of the first measurement up to 260 bar, the half pressure exceeded the measuring range of the bridge voltage (max. 19.5 mV). The values of the bridge voltage at the end of the test were approx. 44 mV, measured with a multimeter. This indicates a further deformation of the CPV even after exceeding the measuring range.

Figure 6: Curves of the first two measurements; bridge voltage over time

In the second test (Fig. 6, right) no further change in stress was measured despite a renewed increase in pressure from 0 to 260 bar, which indicates a constant state of deformation. This thesis was confirmed by a detailed examination of the valve block. The valve block has a non-return valve, which kept the pressure inside the CPV almost constant after the first test.

As a result, in the second attempt only the pressure in the supply line increased and decreased, but there was no change in the CPV. The measuring system has shown this condition correctly, so that a malfunction in the valve in front of the attached pressure gauge can be detected. Further investigations are illustrated in Figs. 8 and 9. The curves in Fig. 7 show examples of the measurements carried out in the selected hydrostatic pressure stages, and Fig. 8 also shows the cyclic test.

The conversion of the bridge voltage was carried out with the aid of the output wire length and the change in resistance caused by the geometric change (change in length) of the wires during structural loading. The measurement curves from 50 bar to 75 bar and 75 bar to 100 bar were carried out with a pressure intensifier. This caused a spontaneous increase of the pressure from 0 bar to the first SET value within a very short time, which is impressively illustrated by the measurement curves, which follow the deformations of the pressure vessel caused by the increase in pressure without any noticeable time delay.

Figure 7: Evaluation of the experiments

All further tests were carried out without pressure intensifiers with a pressure increase of 2 bar/s. The pressure increase was then reduced to a minimum. The measured values were recorded with a temporal resolution of 0.1 s.

Figure 8: Measured values of the deformation measurement during the cyclic loading of the pressure vessel between 25 and 100 bar

In the measurement series, it is evident that the measured values at 75 bar are approximately the same. The same can be seen in the measurement curves 150 bar at 200 bar and the creep rupture test at 200 bar. The maximum values of the other curves sometimes deviate by up to 0.06 % strain. This error can probably be traced back to the renewed calibration of the measuring bridge. In order to be able to exclude this error, the last test was a cyclic loading in time steps of 10 s and a pressure interval between 25 and 100 bar (see Fig. 8).

In the first interval, the maximum pressure in the CPV could not be reached within 10 s, which is due to a too low media volume in the burst test rig. This was not able to provide the required volume within the previous 10 s time to build up the required pressure in the CPV. This correlation is not visible in Fig. 11, since the cyclic pressure stages are recorded exclusively in the form of the last cycle. The cycles shown above serve only to illustrate the experiment. All further cycles took place under the defined conditions. It can be clearly seen that all states lead to the same deformation or elongation state. Deviations of 0.008 % strain in the upper range and 0.014 % strain in the lower range are negligible and disappear in the electronic noise of the measuring system.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed measuring system based on metal alloys is comparatively inexpensive and has very good processing properties, in particular with suitability for integration into the winding process. Specially designed unwinding devices allow direct processing of the wires together with the reinforcing fibers and thermosetting resin systems.

With the help of measurements on a commercially available CPV, the functionality of the wires could be impressively demonstrated, confirming the great potential of the SHM system produced on metal wires in the direct process, in particular due to the high accuracy and the very low material and processing costs. The stability of the measuring system was also positively tested over one cycle. Further investigations on the impact behaviour and on thermally induced loads are still pending.

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